

Bioeconomy Science Institute Engagement Strategy with Wikimedia Platforms

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Table of Contents

Executive summary	2
Wikimedia Commons.....	2
Wikidata.....	2
Staff and wider engagement with Wikimedia platforms.....	3
Funding.....	3
Introduction	4
Wikimedia Commons	6
Specimen images.....	6
Staff images.....	7
Archival images, digitised field journals and other publications.....	7
Suggested High Impact Project.....	9
Documentation.....	9
Informing the Wiki editing community in New Zealand.....	10
Impact metrics.....	11
Wikidata	13
Biota of New Zealand identifiers.....	13
New Zealand Organism Register identifiers.....	14
Wikidata items for Taxa.....	15
Type specimen Wikidata items.....	15
Wikidata items for people.....	16
Publications by employees or affiliates of BSI.....	18
Scholarly article Wikidata items.....	19
Conflict of Interest and self-promotion	20
BSI Staff contributions to Wikimedia platforms	20
Next engagement steps	21
Conclusion	21

Executive summary

The Wikimedia movement is a global collaboration whose mission is to share educational content with the world. By undertaking engagement between BSI and the Wikimedia movement, BSI can improve the New Zealand public's access to and reuse of knowledge generated by BSI groups and staff, empower BSI to reuse Wikimedia platform data and identifiers, and collaborate to enrich, reuse and disseminate knowledge relating to the bioeconomy. Greater engagement can also aid the development of an integrated approach to BSI community engagement.

Of particular importance to this collaboration are the multiple nationally significant biological collections held by BSI. These collections are critical for supporting sustainable land use, informing biosecurity solutions as well as understanding and protecting Aotearoa New Zealand's unique biodiversity.

By ensuring BSI data and images from these collections are added or linked to Wikimedia platforms, BSI can help ensure internet search engines and AI applications deliver information and accurate results to the wide variety of New Zealand individuals and communities who use those methods to retrieve knowledge.

With these aims in mind this strategy document recommends that BSI encourage their staff to make data and images accessible online so these can be used by the Wiki community; specifically:

Wikimedia Commons

- images, particularly type specimen images, to be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons as part of the imaging workflow of the BSI.
- BSI staff photographs, archives (e.g. images and notebooks from field collecting, surveys, workshops) and illustrations, to be considered for upload to Wikimedia Commons.

Impact metrics on the reuse of these images can be collated and reported to BSI management to indicate the success of such uploads.

Wikidata

- BSI staff make BSI database identifiers, particularly the Biota of New Zealand and New Zealand Organism Register identifiers, available to the Wikimedia community to add to appropriate Wikidata taxon items.

- Where needed and appropriate for BSI workflows, BSI staff create type specimen Wikidata items for type specimens held in the nationally significant natural history collections overseen by BSI.
- Where needed and appropriate for BSI workflows, BSI staff create or enrich Wikidata items for all specimen collectors and determiners associated with the nationally significant natural history collections overseen by BSI. BSI may wish to consider roundtripping those identifiers into BSI collection management systems and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).
- Where needed for scholarly impact metrics, BSI library staff may wish to consider ensuring scholarly articles generated by BSI staff have Wikidata items created for them and link those items to the Wikidata items for those authors.

Staff and wider engagement with Wikimedia platforms

- BSI explore incorporating editing Wikimedia platforms should public engagement form a part of a staff member's role.
- BSI increasingly work with Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand as well as local editing communities to create opportunities to engage the wider New Zealand public with BSI knowledge and content.
- BSI consider including the sharing of knowledge, data or content with Wikimedia platforms as part of relevant BSI project funding applications.

Funding

This project was funded by both Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand and BSI. It received SSIF Infrastructure funding for the Nationally Significant Collections & Databases to Landcare Research, New Zealand (projects PRJ5161).

Introduction

The Wikimedia movement is a global collaboration whose mission is to bring free educational content to the world. This effort centers around a group of inter-related projects including the online encyclopedia Wikipedia, the knowledge graph Wikidata, the image repository Wikimedia Commons and others (Wikimedia platforms), all of which aim to create, share and encourage the reuse of free knowledge of all kinds.¹

By engaging with the Wikimedia movement and sharing expert knowledge sourced from its nationally significant scientific collections, databases, and publications, the New Zealand Bioeconomy Science Institute (BSI) will increase the discoverability, accessibility and reusability of those publicly owned or funded resources.

This enhancing of findability, accessibility and reusability of BSI collections and data can help inform New Zealanders in general, and those involved in the New Zealand bioeconomy specifically, about BSI sourced information on topics as wide ranging as biodiversity research, land management, conservation, biocontrol, biodiversity systematics and climate change.

Information on Wikimedia platforms is used by internet search engines such as Google to inform internet search results and by virtual assistants such as Alexa and Siri to inform answers to queries.^{2 3} Wikimedia platforms are also a source of information for multitudes of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications.⁴ By ensuring BSI content is added or linked to Wikimedia platforms, BSI can help ensure internet search engines and AI applications deliver accurate information to the wide variety of New Zealand based individuals and communities who use those methods to retrieve knowledge.

¹ Getting started for GLAMs. *Wikimedia Foundation*. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:GLAM/Getting_started) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:GLAM/Getting_started Retrieved May 25, 2026.

² Overview of Wikimedia Foundation and Google Partnership. *Wikimedia Foundation*. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Overview_of_Wikimedia_Foundation_and_Google_Partnership) https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Overview_of_Wikimedia_Foundation_and_Google_Partnership Retrieved May 27, 2026.

³ Gross, T. (2019) Inside the Alexa-Friendly World of Wikidata. *Wired*. <https://www.wired.com/story/inside-the-alex-friently-world-of-wikidata/> Retrieved May 27, 2026

⁴ Luth, E. (2024) The Use of Wikipedia, Wikimedia, and Open Access Content for Artificial Intelligence and Text and Data Mining. *Stockholm University Intellectual Property Law Review*. 7(1) 37-43 https://stockholmplawreview.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/SIPLR2024_nr2_6_Luth.pdf Retrieved May 27, 2026

Sharing data and images on Wikimedia platforms has the potential to improve staff efficiencies in the retrieval of that knowledge. It can provide BSI with the opportunity to take advantage of community curated structured data added to relevant Wikidata items as well as images shared by BSI on Wikimedia Commons. This can empower BSI to link to or reuse that data in BSI catalogues and databases.⁵

The addition of BSI collection images, data and knowledge into Wikimedia platforms can also assist with efforts to ensure that content has improved security and resilience by providing a de facto digital backup. Disasters can and have adversely affected natural history collections. Examples include the fire at the National Museum of Brazil or the ransomware and data breaches at the the Museum für Naturkunde in Berlin.^{6 7} By ensuring BSI images and data are added to Wikimedia platforms, BSI can go some way in ensuring this information is secure from such catastrophes.

This strategy will outline a variety of recommendations on how BSI can add content to Wikimedia platforms. It will include links to documentation for workflows that can assist BSI staff to contribute to Wikimedia platforms to increase the discoverability of, and engagement with, the nationally significant natural history collections, databases and publications created and maintained by BSI. It also suggests methods in which BSI knowledge systems can be enhanced by linking to or reusing content made accessible via those Wikimedia platforms.

This strategy focuses on Wikimedia Commons and Wikidata as the two key platforms to increase access and visibility of BSI images and data.

⁵ Zeinstra, M. (2019) Research report – Returning Commons community metadata additions and corrections to source. *IP Squared*. [CC BY 4.0](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Research_Report_%E2%80%93_Returning_commons_community_metadata_additions_and_corrections_to_source.pdf). https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Research_Report_%E2%80%93_Returning_commons_community_metadata_additions_and_corrections_to_source.pdf Retrieved May 27, 2026

⁶ Dreyfuss, E. (2018) Brazil's Museum Fire Proves Cultural Memory Needs a Digital Backup. *Wired*. <https://www.wired.com/story/brazil-museum-fire-digital-archives/> Retrieved May 27, 2026

⁷ Dams, J. (2025) When a T-Rex Gets Hacked: Inside Germany's Digital Stone Age *From Berlin with Insight* <https://fromberlinwithinsight.substack.com/p/when-a-t-rex-gets-hacked-inside-germanys> Retrieved May 27, 2026

Wikimedia Commons

Wikimedia Commons is a media file repository "that makes available public domain and freely-licensed educational media content to all, and that acts as a common repository for the various projects of the Wikimedia Foundation".^{8 9}

As BSI uses an open Creative Commons Attribution copyright licence (CC BY 4.0) on many of its images, these images are able to be shared in Wikimedia Commons.

There are three main areas where greater impact can be achieved: images of specimens, images of staff, and archival images.

Specimen images

We recommend that BSI staff upload notable specimen images to Wikimedia Commons. Natural history collection type specimen images in Wikimedia Commons would be particularly impactful. For example, type specimen images document the specific physical specimen used by taxonomists as a basis for the scientific name of the species.

By ensuring these images are shared with Wikimedia Commons it is highly likely these images would be preferred by editors and added to Wikipedia articles and Wikidata items. This would provide a further pathway for New Zealanders and others to access information on these important specimens, the species they represent and the knowledge BSI holds about these specimens and species.

Uploading these images into Wikimedia Commons would also make them available for reuse, not just in Wikipedia articles and on Wikidata items, but also on third party websites and databases. Images would be attributed to BSI, and therefore promote BSI as a trusted source for biodiversity knowledge.

Examples of reuse can include in citizen science platforms such as iNaturalist (<https://www.inaturalist.org>), where the images can be imported into iNaturalist species pages directly from Wikimedia Commons, or websites such as the Atlas of Living Australia (<https://www.ala.org.au/>), which ingests relevant English Wikipedia species articles and any images found in the body of those articles. These sites help with the identification of pest species and can provide information on biological traits such as host species and ecological traits such as species range.

⁸ Wikimedia Commons. *Wikimedia Foundation*. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikimedia_Commons) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikimedia_Commons Retrieved May 25, 2026.

⁹ Commons:Project scope. *Wikimedia Foundation*. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Project_scope) https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Project_scope Retrieved May 25, 2026.

It is recommended that the uploading of specimen images to Wikimedia Commons be made part of the imaging workflow of the BSI. Staff managing the imaging process could, as part of that workflow, periodically upload batches of specimen images to Wikimedia Commons. This process is able to be undertaken relatively seamlessly via OpenRefine (<https://openrefine.org/>) and should be in addition to the sharing of specimen images to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

Staff images

Another type of image that may be particularly impactful for BSI to add to Wikimedia Commons are images of BSI staff. Profile or headshot images as well as images of staff undertaking tasks related to their employment have the potential to be reused for many purposes including marketing and communication of BSI goals and achievements.

As these images can be easily downloaded from Wikimedia Commons with appropriate attribution statements, adding such images to Wikimedia Commons can facilitate access for third parties. These third parties may include journalists, for use in newspaper or magazine articles, conference organisers, for use on conference websites, and even BSI staff themselves, for use in publications or internal communications. These images can also be used to enrich Wikipedia articles and Wikidata items relating to BSI staff and occupations.

Where such uploads to Wikimedia Commons are being considered, the BSI staff member undertaking such uploads should take into account the rights of the living individuals depicted by the images. For further information see Wikimedia Commons official guidance for photographs of identifiable living people https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons:Photographs_of_identifiable_people

Archival images, digitised field journals and other publications

Digitised images, illustrations, field journals and notable publications created by BSI or by its predecessor institutions and held in the BSI archives, could also be considered by BSI for upload to Wikimedia Commons. However the copyright status or licensing of such resources should be carefully considered prior to any upload. Significance should also be assessed to ensure those works most likely to create impact are selected for upload.

Uploads of archival BSI images and scientific illustrations to Wikimedia Commons have been undertaken prior to and during the 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence placement. Examples include an upload of images from the archives of the now defunct Department of Scientific and Industrial Research

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:Images_from_the_DSIR and an

upload of Allan Herbarium botanist handwriting samples

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:Allan_herbarium_handwriting_samples.

These images have been made use of by the Wikimedia editing community both in Wikipedia articles and Wikidata items and have led to a better understanding of New Zealand's natural environment collecting history.

Scientific illustrations are a particularly significant contribution to Wikimedia Commons. The Des Helmore illustration upload undertaken during Mike Dickison's Wikimedian at Large placement with Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research in 2018 is an impactful example. As can be seen below, these illustrations have been used in multiple Wikimedia platforms including different language Wikipedias and also Wikidata. As a result of this reuse, in January 2026 alone, these illustrations have been seen by over 37,000 viewers of those Wikipedia articles.

Wiki	Distinct files used	Pages using files	Total file usages	Page views for 2026-01
www.wikidata.org	358	394	406	652
ceb.wikipedia.org	135	155	166	59
en.wikipedia.org	120	621	638	33,826
nl.wikipedia.org	59	63	63	6
sv.wikipedia.org	55	63	63	25
species.wikimedia.org	38	48	48	67
pt.wikipedia.org	27	28	28	19
es.wikipedia.org	26	27	29	63
fr.wikipedia.org	19	17	25	1,557
no.wikipedia.org	17	19	19	0
Total	388	1,612	1,672	37,577

Page view statistics for the month of January, 2026 of Des Helmore illustrations. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

<https://glamtools.toolforge.org/glamorous/?mode=category&text=Illustrations%20by%20Des%20Helmore> Retrieved May 29, 2026.

Suggested High Impact Project

A potential project opportunity exists as the New Zealand Fungorium holds more than 2800 scientifically and historically important illustrations of New Zealand fungi. These images are publicly accessible on both the Biota of New Zealand and the Systematics Collections Data databases but are not downloadable nor reusable.¹⁰ It appears that while the original illustrations are now owned by the BSI, the copyright in those illustrations may have been retained by the original creators, mycologists Marie Taylor, Barbara Segedin, and Greta Stevenson, or their heirs.

These illustrations would be a significant addition to the Wikimedia Commons as they provide details such as the colour and size of the fungi in the National Fungorium collection. Such details are lost when the fungi specimens are dried for storage. These illustrations are particularly important as many were created by three women mycologists, all of whom made rich contributions to New Zealand's biodiversity knowledge.

BSI staff or a summer student intern, perhaps sourced from the Auckland War Memorial Museum Summer Student Programme (<https://www.aucklandmuseum.com/discover/research/opportunities/sheldon-werner-summer-studentship-programme>), could investigate the state of copyright of these images. If necessary, staff or the intern could negotiate with the heirs of the illustrators to obtain an open Creative Commons copyright licence to allow the reuse of those illustrations.

This would enable the upload of these illustrations to Wikimedia Commons empowering reuse on Wikipedia and Wikidata, allowing for the possible linking of these illustrations to the relevant specimen records in the BSI Systematics Collections Database as well as to the GBIF occurrence record via structured data statements attached to the image file in Wikimedia Commons.

Documentation

Documentation has been created during the 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence to help guide staff in the upload of images the copyright of which is owned by BSI. A complete list of the documentation generated during the Wikimedian in Residence can be found at this link

<https://zenodo.org/communities/nzbsiwir/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>.

¹⁰ About the NZ Fungorium. Bioeconomy Science Institute. <https://www.landcareresearch.co.nz/tools-and-resources/collections/new-zealand-fungorium-pdd-te-kohinga-hekaheka-o-aotearoa/about-the-nz-fungorium> Retrieved May 29, 2026.

This includes a publication to support the upload of images by a BSI employee [Wikimedia Commons uploads : Uploading of Images by an employee of the copyright holder](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17634556) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17634556>)

A publication was also produced to support BSI staff in bulk uploading specimen images via OpenRefine [Uploading specimen images via OpenRefine into Wikimedia Commons](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18970160) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18970160>).

Where BSI staff are uploading type specimen images to Wikimedia Commons it is recommended they follow the [Wikimedia Commons data model for Natural History specimen images](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880400>). This document was also produced during the 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence, as was a cross walk documentation showing how this Wikimedia Commons structured data model relates to the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) Darwin Core standard (<https://dwc.tdwg.org/>). See [Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikimedia Commons + SDC](https://zenodo.org/records/18881782) (<https://zenodo.org/records/18881782>). Following this model will ensure consistency in uploads and that appropriate metadata is added to files uploaded to Wikimedia Commons.

Informing the Wiki editing community in New Zealand

Where uploads of BSI images to Wikimedia Commons are undertaken by staff, we recommend that those staff reach out to Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand (info@wikimedia.nz) to publicise the uploads to the wider Wiki editing community in New Zealand. This will encourage volunteer editors to make use of those images in Wikipedia and Wikidata thus quickly increasing the impact of those uploads.

Undertaking such uploads can also allow the BSI to take advantage of any metadata added to such images by the wider Wikimedia editing communities by ingesting or linking to this enriched information back into BSI databases.¹¹

¹¹ Zeinstra, M. (2019) Research report – Returning Commons community metadata additions and corrections to source. *IP Squared*. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Retrieved May 29, 2026. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Research_Report_%E2%80%93_Returning_commons_community_metadata_additions_and_corrections_to_source.pdf Retrieved May 27, 2026

Impact metrics

Currently there is no simple way to track the reuse of images BSI or its predecessors have uploaded to Wikimedia Commons. This is because Wikimedia Commons does not track the downloading of such images.

However several tools exist within Wikimedia platforms to estimate the use of images within WikiProjects. In January 2026, the BSI Wikimedian in Residence placed the Commons Impact Metrics tool (https://wikitech.wikimedia.org/wiki/Commons_Impact_Metrics) on the overarching Wikimedia Commons category Category:Landcare Research (https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Category:Landcare_Research) thus providing one method to obtain impact metrics for what are now BSI owned images.

From February 2026 this tool has tracked the monthly page views of Wikipedia pages that contain each BSI image. These metrics assume that anyone who reads the article also views the image. This tool can be used as a rough gauge of impact.

As seen below, in the three months this tool has been placed on Category:Landcare Research, BSI images placed on Wikipedia pages have been viewed just under 1 million times. It is recommended that these metrics be reported to appropriate BSI managers as an indication of the impact of sharing BSI images with Wikimedia platforms.

Wikidata

Wikidata is a knowledge base made up of linked structured data. It acts as a central storage for the structured data for Wikimedia sister projects including the many language Wikipedias and Wikimedia Commons. Wikidata has over 43,000 active editors. It has over 120 million items all of which are interconnected.¹²

BSI nationally significant collections and databases contain data that can be shared with Wikidata. Such sharing creates new pathways of discovery for BSI data and content. This sharing also provides the BSI the opportunity to link to appropriate Wikidata items. In addition BSI staff could save significant amounts of time by ingesting data attached to those Wikidata items into the BSI collection management system or other BSI databases. This sharing also empowers multiple communities around New Zealand to gain access to that knowledge and facilitates the reuse of BSI's content, data and expert knowledge to support New Zealand's bioeconomy.

Biota of New Zealand identifiers

This strategy recommends that the BSI database Biota of New Zealand identifiers be added to appropriate taxon items. A Wikidata property, the Biota of New Zealand ID property (P12292 <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P12292>), already exists to facilitate this task. Although many of the identifiers from Biota of New Zealand database have already been placed on appropriate Wikidata taxon items, this database is continually being updated and new identifiers continue to be created.

By encouraging the regular uploading of those new identifiers and attaching them to appropriate Wikidata items BSI can ensure the wider Wiki community as well as the New Zealand public has another avenue of access to data contained in this nationally significant database.

Documentation has been created during the 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence to support Wikidata editors and BSI staff wanting to undertake this task. See [Biota of New Zealand IDs to Wikidata Workflow](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18295158) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18295158>).

¹² Wikidata:Statistics. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Statistics) <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Statistics> Retrieved May 28, 2026

By encouraging the Biota of New Zealand identifier being added to appropriate Wikidata items BSI gains the ability to link to those taxa items either in appropriate collection management systems or via other databases. BSI is then able to ingest and reuse any data contained within or linked to in those Wikidata items, for example other third party institutional or database identifiers.¹³

New Zealand Organism Register identifiers

If a revitalisation of the New Zealand Organisms Register eventuates, we recommend BSI also encourages the linking of NZOR identifiers to taxon Wikidata items. A Wikidata property already exists for the NZOR database - the New Zealand Organisms Register ID property (P2752 <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P2752>). Fortunately significant linking of this identifier to appropriate taxon Wikidata items has already taken place on Wikidata. However should new identifiers be created, the linking of these new identifiers could also be supported.

This linking is particularly impactful as the NZOR id is a database identifier that appears in the taxon identifiers box at the bottom of relevant English Wikipedia articles. See for example the Wikidata item for *Aenetus virescens* <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q507767>, which contains links to both the Biota of New Zealand and NZOR identifiers, and the English Wikipedia article for that species https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/P%C5%ABriri_moth, where the NZOR id is displayed in the taxon identifiers box at the bottom of that article.

As this taxon box is part of the Wikipedia article, any third party websites reusing that article will also ingest that taxon identifiers box. By supporting the addition of the NZOR id to relevant taxon Wikidata items, BSI ensures New Zealanders and others have improved access to the nationally significant NZOR database and the data stored there.

¹³ Meiners, H.-L. and Bulle, K. (2025) Disrupting the Dust: Identifier Properties and the Future of Cultural Heritage Metadata in Wikidata, *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 11(1), p. 65. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.412>

Wikidata items for Taxa

The work of ensuring the Biota of New Zealand ID and the NZOR ID be linked to appropriate taxa items may require the creation of new Wikidata items for those taxa. The 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence published documentation to support BSI employees and others to manually create Wikidata taxon items. See [Creating a new Wikidata taxon item](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17807008) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17807008>).

The bulk creation via OpenRefine of Wikidata items for taxa has been covered in the above mentioned [Biota of New Zealand IDs to Wikidata Workflow](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18295158) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18295158>) documentation.

Type specimen Wikidata items

It is recommended that, where needed and appropriate for BSI workflows, BSI staff create Wikidata items for type specimens held in BSI collections. Doing so will support the discovery of BSI collections, assist with the interoperability of BSI data about those specimens, help with the enrichment of other Wikidata items that are linked to BSI databases, and empower the enrichment of metadata for related type specimen images uploaded to Wikimedia Commons.

Undertaking such editing can allow the BSI to take advantage of any metadata added to such Wikidata items by the wider Wikimedia editing communities by ingesting or linking to this enriched information in BSI databases.¹⁴

Where such Wikidata items are created, BSI staff should follow the Wikidata type specimen item data model created during the 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence. See [Wikidata data model for Natural History type specimens](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880276) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18880276>). To help assist with any bulk creation of Wikidata type specimen items this data model has been crosswalked to the TDWG Darwin Core data standard. See the documentation [Crosswalk for Natural History Specimen Data Model - Wikidata](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18881948) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18881948>).

The 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence produced documentation to support BSI staff in their bulk creation via OpenRefine of type specimen Wikidata items. See [Creation of type specimen Wikidata items via OpenRefine](https://zenodo.org/records/18883286) (<https://zenodo.org/records/18883286>).

¹⁴ Zeinstra, M. (2019) Research report – Returning Commons community metadata additions and corrections to source. *IP Squared*. [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Retrieved May 29, 2026. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Research_Report_%E2%80%93_Returning_commons_community_metadata_additions_and_corrections_to_source.pdf Retrieved May 27, 2026

As part of the 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence Wikidata items were created for species holotype specimens held in the New Zealand Arthropod Collection. The OpenRefine project used to undertake this now serves as an exemplar for this type of bulk creation of type specimen Wikidata items. See [New Zealand Arthropod Collection holotype specimen Wikidata upload \(https://zenodo.org/records/18882424\)](https://zenodo.org/records/18882424).

Wikidata items for people

This strategy recommends that, where appropriate and needed for BSI workflows, BSI staff create or enrich Wikidata items for specimen collectors and determiners held in the nationally significant natural history collections overseen by BSI. Where Wikidata items are to be created for living people, BSI staff should be cognisant of the Wikidata policy regarding living people https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Living_people.

Undertaking this would empower the wider Wikimedia editing community to aid BSI in disambiguating those collectors and determiners, enriching Wikidata items with associated data such as birth and death dates, whom the collectors or determiners worked for, their areas of expertise, where they were educated, articles and books they published, who they collected with, and what institutions hold their collections. All of which can be linked to and reused in BSI collection management systems or databases and can help provide context to the specimens held in the nationally significant collections overseen by BSI.

Creating Wikidata items for those collectors and determiners also assists editors to connect those items to other institutions' data about those collectors or determiners. Scholarly identifiers such as ORCID <https://orcid.org/>, Google Scholar <https://scholar.google.com/>, Researchgate <https://www.researchgate.net/> and VIAF <https://viaf.org/en> are particularly helpful to add as they aid the linking of collectors and determiners to any publications they may have produced.

We suggest that BSI make efforts to ensure collectors who deposit their collections with BSI and specimen determiners who work on BSI collections have an ORCID identifier and share that identifier with BSI for BSI staff to add to appropriate collection management systems.

We recommend that BSI ensure specimen collectors and determiners are digitally linked to the nationally significant collections held by BSI. This process can be expedited by using the website and tool [Bionomia.net](https://www.bionomia.net).

Bionomia takes the collection specimen occurrence data provided by BSI to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), extracts the name strings for the collectors and determiners and suggests to its volunteers either the Wikidata item or ORCID identifier that may relate to the collector or identifier listed on relevant specimens. Bionomia volunteers can then either confirm or reject that suggestion.

Based on these attributions, Bionomia can then produce a profile both for the collector or determiner as well as a profile for the collection dataset in GBIF. By attributing specimens to a collector or determiner, as represented by their Wikidata item or ORCID id, Bionomia scribes can digitally link those people to their relevant specimens.

Bionomia then produces data packages based on this attribution data that can be used by the organisations that provide those datasets to GBIF. These data packages can assist BSI staff with the correction of data issues as they highlight potential data errors. Another data package provided by Bionomia relates to attribution data. This can be used to add “collection items at” statements to appropriate Wikidata items for relevant collectors. This statement links the BSI collection Wikidata item to the Wikidata item for the collectors that have contributed to that collection and helps ensure a list of people who have contributed to that collection can be generated.

During the 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence documentation was created to help guide BSI staff and Wikidata editors in adding such data to Wikidata. See the [Bionomia/OpenRefine/Wikidata "Collection items at" workflow](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18379994) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18379994>).

Where possible it is recommended that BSI link to Wikidata item identifiers (QIDs) for collectors and determiners, or alternatively consider ingesting the data contained in those items, into appropriate BSI collection management systems and databases. As an example of another institution undertaking such linking and ingestion see the Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa's efforts to reuse Wikidata people items in its collection management system.¹⁵

¹⁵ Schrader, L. (2023) Agreeing to agree: Roundtripping people identifiers with Wikidata. *Te Papa Blog* <https://blog.tepapa.govt.nz/2023/12/05/agreeing-to-agree-roundtripping-people-identifiers-with-wikidata/> Retrieved May 28, 2026

Publications by employees or affiliates of BSI

We suggest that BSI library staff ensure scholarly articles generated by staff have Wikidata items created for them and that those items are linked to the Wikidata items for those authors. This has the potential to encourage access to and citation of these BSI related publications.

This effort is made easier for BSI staff if such articles have a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) whose metadata is stored in a registry for peer reviewed scholarly articles such as CrossRef <https://www.crossref.org/>.

BSI Library staff may wish to consider creating retrospective DOIs for historical articles and books published by BSI predecessor institutions. These DOIs will provide an alternative method of accessing BSI publications and the knowledge contained within them. Then adding the DOI and its associated metadata about those publications to Wikidata will amplify this alternative avenue of access to BSI held knowledge and can assist in improving the impact of those publications.

The existence of a DOI for a publication allows for the use of Wikidata tools, such as BHLtoWiki <https://bhl2wiki.herokuapp.com/>, and workflows, such as Zotero to Wikidata <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Zotero> and DOI to Quickstatement via Scholia <https://scholia.toolforge.org/id-to-quickstatements>, to streamline the creation of Wikidata items.

Alternatively bulk creation of Wikidata items can also be undertaken via OpenRefine. BSI staff can use OpenRefine to first check whether those publications are already in Wikidata and then to create Wikidata items for each of the publications missing a Wikidata item. The data model for scholarly articles can be found here https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_Wikidata_for_research/Data_models/Scholarly_article.

Adding such publications to Wikidata empowers the linking of those articles to the staff member that authored them, the main subjects of the publication, the other publications cited in the article, the funder of the publication, where the publication can be accessed on the internet, and any identifiers that may relate to that publication.

This linking to authors can ensure that BSI has an alternative avenue to gauge the impact of publications by staff and can empower the use of the free scholarly profile tool Scholia <https://qlever.scholia.wiki/>. The main subject statements can ensure BSI articles can be collated and more easily discovered by those wanting to make use of the same.

Adding publications cited helps integrate BSI articles into the wider bibliographic network, again assisting with the finding and reusing of those articles and improving the impact of these publications. Linking to the funding for such publications helps map financial resources to research outputs and can again assist with tracing the impact of that funding on research. Linking to the URL where the work can be found can drive web traffic to such resources as the BSI digital library and other BSI websites. Adding identifiers to scholarly article Wikidata items can empower BSI library staff to reuse those identifiers in the BSI library catalogue.

Scholarly article Wikidata items

Once publications have Wikidata items created for them it is then possible to link those publications to the Wikidata items for the BSI natural history collections or the datasets generated from those collections and used to help create those publications. This linking may require the further creation of Wikidata items for relevant datasets.

The 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence produced documentation guiding BSI staff and Wikidata editors on how to link publications to BSI collections. See [Linking publications to collections : Adding cites work, uses or acknowledges statements to Wikidata \(https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17635242\)](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17635242).

The 2025-2026 Wikimedian in Residence also produced documentation on how to appropriately share the knowledge and content contained in a scholarly publication with Wikipedia, Wikidata and Wikimedia Commons to enrich those platforms. See ["Wikifying" a scholarly publication \(https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17635843\)](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17635843). This "wikifying" can benefit BSI by helping gauge the impact of that publication. However we emphasise that a researcher should not treat Wikipedia as a place of self promotion. See also the Wikipedia and Conflict of Interest sections below.¹⁶

¹⁶ Help:Wikipedia editing for researchers, scholars, and academics. Wikimedia Foundation. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Help:Wikipedia_editing_for_researchers_scholars_and_academics](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Help:Wikipedia_editing_for_researchers_scholars_and_academics)
Retrieved June 1, 2026.

Conflict of Interest and self-promotion

Unlike the addition of images to Wikimedia Commons, the editing of Wikidata items and especially Wikipedia articles by BSI staff has the potential to be problematic.

For Wikidata, as any statements added to a Wikidata item should be referenced, the platform tends to tolerate topic experts contributing to the subject in which they are experts so long as the edits are neutral. However BSI staff editing during their employment would be classed as paid contributors and so therefore should explicitly declare their affiliation.

For Wikipedia, it is possible for BSI staff to edit Wikipedia articles in their area of expertise. However they should not edit articles in which they have a conflict of interest nor should they edit for the purpose of boosting the coverage of BSI, BSI staff or research publications created by staff. If BSI staff infringe the conflict of interest editing policy or develop a reputation as a self-promoter, either on Wikidata or Wikipedia, they are likely to get themselves blocked as an editor and their contributions undone or deleted.^{17 18}

BSI Staff contributions to Wikimedia platforms

Several staff members of BSI are already contributing their expert knowledge to Wikipedia articles, Wikidata and Wikimedia Commons in their own time. If staff contracts include professional development clauses, BSI could consider allowing training in Wikimedia editing and data tools like OpenRefine to fulfill these requirements.

Alternatively, we suggest that BSI permit any staff with outreach duties to edit Wikimedia platforms in fulfillment of those obligations. As an example of an institution that allows contributing to Wikimedia platforms during work time see Te Papa and their initiative of getting their staff involved in editing Wikipedia.¹⁹

¹⁷ Conflict of interest. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Conflict_of_interest) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikipedia:Conflict_of_interest Retrieved June 1, 2026

¹⁸ Help:Wikipedia editing for researchers, scholars, and academics. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Help:Wikipedia_editing_for_researchers_scholars_and_academics) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Help:Wikipedia_editing_for_researchers_scholars_and_academics Retrieved June 1, 2026.

¹⁹ Shrader, L. (2025) How to (actually) get your GLAM using Wikipedia. *Te Papa Blog*. <https://blog.tepapa.govt.nz/2025/05/06/how-to-actually-get-your-glam-using-wikipedia/> Retrieved June 1, 2026

Sharing knowledge, data or content with Wikimedia platforms could also be included as part of BSI project funding applications. This would specifically allow for the funding of staff hours needed to contribute project images, data and content to Wikimedia platforms.

Next engagement steps

BSI could consider exploring the possibility of obtaining a summer student intern to work on an appropriate project. This summer internship could be supported through the Auckland War Memorial Museum Summer Student Programme (<https://www.aucklandmuseum.com/discover/research/opportunities/sheldon-werner-summer-studentship-programme>).

If BSI wishes to continue to encourage the sharing of BSI content in various Wikimedia platforms, BSI could consider working with the Auckland, Christchurch and wider New Zealand editing communities and Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand specifically to host or support editathons or Wikiblitzes related to BSI content.

These events can encourage new and existing Wiki editors to reuse BSI content and images in Wikipedia and Wikidata. Such events could also educate Wiki editors on BSI resources such as BSI collections and databases as well as the BSI digital library and BSI related publications, again encouraging reuse of the same in various Wikimedia platforms.

Conclusion

By integrating BSI knowledge into the Wikimedia movement, the BSI can amplify the accessibility of its collections, databases and publications via internet search engines and AI applications while at the same time fostering knowledge sharing by the Wiki community and the wider New Zealand public. This strategy can also enhance BSI data security against disasters, can improve staff efficiency through improved access to community-curated data, and can help fulfill BSI's mandate to share biodiversity-related knowledge with diverse communities.